

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC)

**A.E. Bras
V.H.J. van der Velden**

Laboratory Medical Immunology (LMI), Department of Immunology, Erasmus Medical Center, Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Correspondence: a.e.bras@gmail.com / a.bras@erasmusmc.nl / v.h.j.vandervelden@erasmusmc.nl

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Historic Overview Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵

Historic Overview Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases

Base 13 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathbf{8460}_{10} \quad \mathbf{3B0A}_{13} \\ \hline -1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^{6_{13}}+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13} \\ \hline \mathbf{605}_{10} \quad \mathbf{377}_{13} \\ \hline CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13} \\ \hline \end{array}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} -1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10} \\ \hline 167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10} \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

$$\begin{array}{c} 1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad 6 \quad 7 \quad 8 \quad 9 \quad A \quad B \quad C \quad + \quad - \quad * \quad / \quad ^ \quad (\quad) \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Digits 1 up to C occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BC \\ \hline CB+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BC \\ \hline CB+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BC \\ \hline CB+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BC \\ \hline CB+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$$\begin{array}{c} -1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BC \\ \hline CB+A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{c} (1+2-3)*(45*-(6^7)+8-9ABC) \\ \hline (1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9ABC) \\ \hline (1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9ABC) \\ \hline (-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9ABC) \\ \hline -(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9))*ABC) \\ \hline (CBA98+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1) \\ \hline (CBA98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1) \\ \hline (CBA98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1) \\ \hline (CBA98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1) \\ \hline -(CBA*(9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1) \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 13 crazy sequential representations for 0000_{13} up to CCC_{13}

Expected number of representations = $2_{13} + CCCC_{13} + CCCC_{13} = 20000_{13} = 57122_{10}$

Results

57111_{10} out of 57122_{10} were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing	None
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Decreasing	2A62, 2B12, 5243, 5921, 6415, 7281, 7B75, 8C3B, 9083, A402, B676
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Notes

Authors consider base 13 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Other Bases

Authors also identified genuine crazy sequential representations for other bases:

Date	Title
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

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